

(*Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025*)

Sunflower Extraction's Potential to Reduce Lead-Induced Toxicity in Lead-Contaminated Soil

¹Aminu, N., ²Gumi, A. M., ¹Magami, I.M., ¹Abdussamiu, N. A., ¹Muhammad, Z. M., ³Muhammad, A. B. and ⁴Muhammad, A.

¹Department of Biology, Faculty of Chemical & Life Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

²Department of Plant Science, Faculty of Chemical & Life Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

³Department of Energy & Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical & Life Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

⁴Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences, State College of Basic and Remedial Studies Sokoto.

*Correspondance: nnasallah.na@gmail.com; Phone: 08062657101

Abstract

*The presence of Lead (Pb) in the environment has become widespread, mainly due to human activities and it's becoming a major concern globally. This study aimed to determine the responses of Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) to varying concentrations of lead and to evaluate its bioaccumulation potentials. Sunflower seedlings (4-weeks old) were spiked once with different concentrations (0, 100, 200 and 500 mM) of lead oxide solutions and observed weekly for 2 weeks. The growth, biomass and lead (Pb) content of sunflower in different treatments was measured. The results revealed that lead significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced plant height, number of leaves, biomass of shoot and roots. The control had the highest plant height of 35cm while 500 mM treatment had the shortest length of 25cm. For shoot and root biomass, the control had the highest biomass of 13.2g and 3.5g respectively while 100 mM treatment had the lowest biomass of 10.8g and 1.1g respectively for shoot and root. The lead (Pb) concentrations in shoot of Sunflower significantly ($p < 0.005$) increased with increasing concentrations with the highest content (0.478 mg/kg) in 500 mM treatment while the control (0 mM) had the lowest (0.006 mg/Kg) lead concentrations. Lead uptake in the roots showed that 500 mM treatment had the highest (0.515mg/Kg) lead content while the control (0 mM) had the lowest (0.006mg/Kg) lead content. Overall, Sunflower showed differential response and uptake of lead to varying concentrations of lead. Sunflower can serve as a sentinel and good candidate in cleaning lead polluted soils.*

Keywords: *Helianthus annuus*, Phytoremediation, Lead, Bioaccumulation, Lead Oxide

Introduction

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) is the most potential oil seed crop for edible oil production in the world. Besides, the third most important oilseed crop in Pakistan after the Rapeseed and Mustard. The first decade of this century had perceived a substantial improvement in the crop yield of sunflower; however, the average crop yield has gradually decreased since 2010 (Altaf et al.,2020). This decrease could be ascribed

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

to the shorter availability of mineral fertilizers, overexploitation of marginal land and toxic heavy metals pollution in the soil (Rehman et al.,2022). Thus, it needs to adopt modern and sustainable approaches to fulfil fertilizer resilience and improve plant growth and soil health. Lead (Pb) is a widely distributed trace element with severe health impacts such as brain damage and central nervous system disorders (Ashraf et al.,2021; Liu et al.,2022). Several sources of Pb exposure to the environment, particularly rock weathering, extensive use of pesticides, leaded gasoline, molting paint chips, batteries, and wastewater irrigation have been overwhelmed (Xie et al.,2020). Most countries around the world, including the United States, China, India, Japan, and Pakistan, have reported that Pb concentration in soils has gradually increased and become a key factor in reducing crop yields (Lyu et al.,2016). Normally, Pb makes stable complexes such as phosphates, carbonates, sulfates, and hydroxides, which deteriorate soil fertility and crop yield. Najeeb et al. (2017) reported that Pb toxicity induces oxidative stress (ROS) that inhibits seeds germination, nutrients assimilation, enzyme activity, and the photosynthetic rate in plants, ultimately affecting the crop yield. In view of this circumstance, the U.S, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the Ministry of Ecology and Environment have settled down the maximum Pb concentration limits (400 mg/kg Agro–field area) for controlling the Pb pollution in the soil (Zhang et al.2019). In recent years, numerous sustainable and environmentally safe techniques have been used to remediate the metals polluted soils (Ashraf et al. 2019; Hou et al.,2020) At present, the adsorption technique is regarded as the most useful and inexpensive approach for Pb-contaminated soils (He et al.2021; Hong et al.2022).In recent decades, sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), as a plant of the family Asteraceae, has attracted much attention for use in phytoextraction, as it could be grown under stressful conditions, such as heavy metal stress. Sunflower can accumulate relatively large amounts of metallic contaminants, besides translocating a good amount of the same from roots to shoots, and producing large quantities of biomass. Ashraf et al.,2021 found that *Helianthus annuus* L. was a robust and suitable plant that could be used for extracting and repairing cadmium, lead, and zinc from soil under certain conditions. Moreover, the success of phytoextraction partially relies on the solubility and availability of metal in soil for root uptake. Usually, heavy metals adsorbed in soil particles are difficult to be integrated by plants.

Statement of the problem

Environmental contamination due to heavy metals have become a matter of great concern over few decades as it poses toxic effects on plants and animals inhabiting the

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

affected region. These pollutants are added in soil and water through industrial discharge, mining, pesticides, fertilizers and automobile exhausts. High contamination of heavy metals in soil and water also pose a potential threat to ecosystem; while their toxic effects limit the agricultural yield, their uptake by plants incorporates them in the food chain causing hazardous health effects (Chen et al.,2020). Trace amounts of heavy metals are potential enough to damage the vital functions of plants such as seed germination, seedling growth, photosynthesis and other physiological events. Heavy metals enter the human body through the gastrointestinal tract, skin, or via inhalation. Toxic metals have proven to be a major threat to human health, mostly because of their ability to cause membrane and DNA damage, and to perturb protein function and enzyme activity.

Materials and methods

Plant Materials and their Sources

The seeds of the selected plant species was collected from matured plants (*Jatropha curcas* L.) and (*Helianthus annuus* L.) growing in the Biological garden and taken to the Herbarium of the Department of plant science, Faculty of Chemical and Life Sciences, UDUS for further identification. The seeds were sorted to remove soil particles, dirt and debris before placed in an oven (at 600C) for 2 days to break the possible dormancy of the seeds. The seeds are stored in air tight containers until used.

Soil Analysis

The soil sample is transfer to a plastic tray for air-drying. Large clods are break up to speed up drying. Large plant residues are removed. The soil is not placed in direct sunlight. After drying, the total sample is weighed, Sieve through a 2 mm sieve, Clods not passing through the sieve are carefully crushed by a pestle and mortar and sieved again. Special features such as coarse concretions are picked out as quantitatively as possible and their content is determined separately. The fraction <2 mm (air-dry fine earth) is homogenized and constitutes the sample that is subjected to the usual laboratory procedures. The soil is analyse to know the heavy metals, toxins that is cyanide derivatives. present before planting the seeds. Soil samples are analyse for physico chemical properties such as texture, colour, pH, nitrate-nitrogen, calcium, magnesium etc. by using soil analysis kit. Respective extraction procedures are followed for analyzing the above properties. Reagents necessary for the analysis were provided in the kit. Physico-chemical properties of the soil are measured, heavy metals constituents and contaminants present are analyse (Farmaha et al., 2020).

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

Solution Formulation and Spiking

Laboratory grade lead oxide (PbO₃) was dissolved in distilled water to make varying concentration of 0, 100, 250 and 500mm concentration of the respective contaminants. The solution is stored in air tight containers until required for use. (Ghani, 2011).

Experimental setup and description

The study was carried out at Tissue Culture in the main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto (UDUS). A pot experiment was conducted in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) Seeds were grown in plastic pots filled with 7kg of soil, 5 seeds were sown at equal distance and one inch deep in soil of corresponding pots, thinning to one-plant after 14 days from sowing. Lead oxide concentrations of 500 mM, 200 mM, 100 mM and 0 mM are used to spike the plants using 100 mL volume of each solution. Lead treatments were added to the soil at one-month seedling age. Stressed induced for two weeks, replicated three times (Hinkelmann and Kempthorne, 2008).

Determination of Leaf Spectroscopy and Pigment Indices

The plants are subjected to spiking with lead after 6 weeks of germination from mild concentration, average concentration to high concentration. After one week of spiking the measurement start using CID (CI-710) leaf spectra machine model CI 710s (spectra View) (CID Bio Science, Inc. Felix Instruments Applied Food Science 1554 NE 3TM Ave, Camas, WA 98607). According to the manufacturer manual there are two ways to take measurement, the live measurement and single measurement mode; previewing live measurement procedure are; place leaf inside of the leaf clip, enable display live measurement in the graph menu and select chosen mode in the home screen, then the start button and save button to record the measurement. Then the red box will be pressed to stop previewing. To take single measurement; leaf was placed inside of the leaf clip, disable display live measurement in the graph menu and the chosen mode will be selected in the home screen, press the start button to take/ save a measurement. All the growth markers are measured (leaf senescence, leaf colour, leaf pattern, leaf fluorescence, leaf pigmentation, chlorophyll contents and carotenoids) on the machine. Measurement continues weekly same day and time (Falcioni et al., 2023).

Analysis of Biomass and Heavy Metals

Plant samples were collected every 7 days and the shoot and roots were separated by stainless blade. All parts were washed with distilled water. Plant samples, including

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

shoots and roots, were dried in an oven at 50°C, and the weights of samples were recorded by a weighing balance. The method develops by Awofolu (2015) was use in digesting the plant samples. A 0.5g sample of plant part in a beaker. 2ml of chloric acid (HClO₄) and 4ml concentrated (65%) nitric acid (HNO₃) will be added and heated on a hot plate until plant parts are digested. It will be allowed to cool and thereafter filter through the Whatman filter paper into a 50 cm³volumetric flask of 50 cm³. The filtrate collected and dilute with 50 cm³ with distilled water. All the filtrate both soil and plant parts will be analyse for heavy metals using microwave plasma atomic emission spectrophotometer (MPAES) (Black,2015). using acetylene/air as a gas mixture.

Statistical analysis

The results obtain was presented as Mean + SD of the 3 replicates used. The data generated on growth, morphology and pigment indices were analysed using two – way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS version 20 statistical package at 5% level of significance ($p \leq 0.05$) and 10% ($p \leq 0.01$). The difference between means was determine using Least Significance Difference (LSD) test.

Results

Growth and Morphological response of Sunflower to varying Concentration of Lead In lead, the results for plant growth parameters, involving plant shoot length (SL), root length (RL)and number of leaves. The height of plant decreased with increasing concentration of lead. The control 0mM recorded the highest height (51cm in week 1and 74cm in week 2) followed by 100mM and 200mM, (29cm in week 1and 62cm in week 2) and (25cm in week 1 and 67cm in week 2) and 500mM had the least value of height (24cm in week 1 and 45cm in week 2) respectively, there is statistical difference between the treatment $p < 0.05$ (Fig. 1).

The number of leaves per plant of sunflower is affected by various concentration of sunflower, the control (0mM) had the highest number of leaves in both weeks (27 in week 1 and 39 in week 2). Followed by 100mM (25 in week 1 and 33 in week 2) and 200mM (24 in week 1 and 32 in week 2). And subsequently 500mM had the least number of leaves (21 in week 1 and 31 in week 2). There is no significance statistical difference between the treatment $p > 0.05$ (Fig. 2). In addition, the result of root height shows no significance statistical difference $p > 0.05$, the control 0mM had the highest height (35cm in week 1 and 29cm in week 2), followed by 100mM and 200mM (25cm

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

in week 1 and 26cm in week 2) and (27cm in week 1 and 24cm in week 2) and 500mM had the least height (25cm in week 1 and 21cm in week 2) respectively (Fig. 3)

Figure 1: plant height with varying concentration of lead

Figure 2: Number of leaves with different concentration of leaf

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

Figure 3: Root length with different concentration of lead

Plant Biomass Determination

The result on the effect of lead on biomass of sunflower in shoot fresh water (SFW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference between the treatment $p > 0.05$, control (0mM) has the highest weight (week 1 86.8g and week 2 73.0g) followed by 100mM and 200mM, (77.1g in week 1 and 42.2g in week 2) and (67.1g in week 1 and 40g in week 2) and 500mM had the least weight (50.7g in week 1 and 38.3g in week, 2) respectively, (Fig. 4).

Furthermore, result on shoot dry weight (SDW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference $p > 0.05$, the control 0mM shows the highest dry matter 13.2g in week 1 and 13.3g in week 2 followed by 100mM and 200mM 11.0g in week 1 and 9.8g in week 2, 10.9g in week 1 and 9.2g in week 2 and 500mM had the least weight 10.0g in week 1 and 7.0g in week 2 respectively, (Fig. 5). The result on the effect of lead on biomass of sunflower in root fresh weight (RFW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference $p > 0.05$, control 0mM has the highest weight (week 1 14.6g and week 2 13.4g) followed by 100mM and 200mM, (11.0g in week 1 and 9.8g in week 2) and (9.9g in week 1 and 9.2g in week 2) and 500mM had the least weight (9.0g in week 1 and 7.8g in week 2) respectively, (Fig. 6). Root dry weight (RDW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference $p > 0.05$, the control 0mM shows the highest dry matter 3.5g in week 1 and 4.2g in week 2 followed by 100mM and 200mM 2.5g in week 1 and 2.3g in week 2, 2.3g in week 1 and 2.3g in week 2 and 500mM had the least weight 1.1g in week 1 and 1.7g in week 2 respectively, (Fig. 7).

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

Figure 4: Fresh weight of shoot with varying concentration of lead

Figure 5: Dry weight of shoot with different concentration of lead

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

Figure 6: Root fresh weigh with varying concentration of lead

Figure 7: Root dry weight with different concentration of lead

Leaf Spectroscopy and Pigment Indices In lead the results revealed that contaminated soils affect all plants survival rates and growth. The result with $p\text{-value} = 0.003 < 0.05$ for PSRI implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels on PSRI of the sunflower at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level 200mM with average value $-0.80 \pm 0.15\text{mM}$ is significantly lesser than lead levels 0mM, 100mM and 500mM with average values $-0.06 \pm 0.01\text{mM}$, $-0.07 \pm 0.02\text{mM}$ and $-0.07 \pm 0.04\text{mM}$ respectively. The result with $p\text{-value} = 0.042 < 0.05$ for CRI1 implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels on CRI1 of the sunflower at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

200mM with average value 0.30 ± 0.15 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead level 100mM 0.24 ± 0.12 mM and lastly are lead at levels 0mM and 100mM with average values 0.03 ± 0.12 , and 0.03 ± 0.13 respectively which equally significant. However, the p -value = $0.392 > 0.05$ for WBI, p -value = $0.705 > 0.05$ for SPAD, p -value = $0.699 > 0.05$ for G, p -value = $0.980 > 0.05$ for CHPLT, p -value = $0.379 > 0.05$ for CPHLA, p -value = $0.317 > 0.05$ for CPHLB, p -value = $0.994 > 0.05$ for ARI1 and p -value = $0.790 > 0.05$ for CCI implied that effects of lead contents at 0mM (control), 100mM, 200mM and 500mM on WBI, SPAD, G, CHPLT, CPHLA, CPHLB, ARI1 and CCI of sunflower are not statistically significant at 5 % level (Table1).

Table 1: Effects of Lead on Some Parameters of Sunflower

Group	WBI	SPAD	PSRI	G	CRI1	CHPLT	CPHLA	CPHLB	ARI1	CCI
0mM	1.14±0.08	19.7±3.53	0.06±0.01 ^b	2.20±0.26	0.03±0.12 ^c	27.5±5.56	10.6±1.23	16.8±3.25	0.003±0.002	6.52±1.62
100mM	1.14±0.15	19.6±2.79	0.07±0.02 ^b	2.33±0.27	0.03±0.13 ^c	26.8±3.97	10.3±1.38	16.4±4.31	0.003±0.002	6.39±1.24
200mM	1.14±0.01	18.97±4.95	0.80±0.15 ^a	2.28±0.25	0.30±0.15 ^a	26.9±3.98	10.4±1.34	16.5±6.08	0.002±0.003	6.27±2.29
500mM	0.980±0.38	17.01±5.14	0.07±0.04 ^b	2.20±0.38	0.24±0.12 ^b	24.9±4.73	9.65±1.70	15.2±3.02	0.002±0.004	5.43±2.12
S.E	0.78	1.859	0.11	0.131	2.012	1.806	0.631	1.174	0.002	0.078
F-stat	0.164	0.473	3.509	0.482	2.947	0.98	0.82	1.065	0.124	0.35
P-value	0.392	0.705	0.003	0.699	0.042	0.337	0.379	0.317	0.994	0.79
Sig.	NS	NS	*	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by the same letter along the columns are not significantly different
 * = significant at 5%, NS = Not Significant, Values=Mean ± SD, SD= Standard deviation

Heavy Metal Analysis and Uptake Bioaccumulation of lead in sunflower shoot and root, the result with p -value = $0.000 < 0.05$ for lead bioaccumulation on sunflower' shoots

(*Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025*)

in the presence of heavy metals implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels of sunflower's shoots at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level 500mM with average value 0.4549 ± 0.0264 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead levels 200mM with average value 0.3545 ± 0.0199 mM, followed by 100 mM with average value 0.2412 ± 0.0253 mM and lastly 0 mM level with average value 0.0098 ± 0.0043 mM (Table 2).

The result $F=10.526$ with $p\text{-value}= 0.000 < 0.05$ for lead bioaccumulation on sunflower's roots in the presence of heavy metals implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level 500 mM with average value 0.5384 ± 0.0307 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead levels 200 mM with average value 0.4637 ± 0.0746 mM, followed by 100mM with average value 0.3417 ± 0.0176 mM and lastly 0 mM level with average value 0.1196 ± 0.2726 mM

Table 2: Bioaccumulation of Lead in shoot and root of Sunflower

Concentrations	Parameters	
	Shoot	Root
0mM	0.0098 ± 0.0043^d	0.1196 ± 0.2726^d
100mM	0.2412 ± 0.0253^c	0.3417 ± 0.0176^c
200mM	0.3545 ± 0.0199^b	0.4637 ± 0.0746^b
500mM	0.4549 ± 0.0264^a	0.5384 ± 0.0307^a
S.E	0.006	0.056
F-stat	970.557	10.526
P-value	0.000	0.000
Sig.	*	*

Total uptake of lead by sunflower by measuring the amount left in soil

The result with $p\text{-value}= 0.000 < 0.05$ for lead accumulated in soil after harvesting implies that there is significant difference between the lead levels left in the soil at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the 500mM treatment with average value 0.6428 ± 0.0577 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead levels 200 mM with average

(*Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025*)

value 0.5619 ± 0.0250 mM, followed by 100mM with average value 0.4465 ± 0.0338 mM and lastly 0mM level with average value 0.0065 ± 0.0028 mM (Table3)

Table 3: Lead accumulated in soil after harvesting with different conc. of lead

Concentrations	Parameter Soil
0mM	0.0065 ± 0.0028^d
100mM	0.4465 ± 0.0338^c
200mM	0.5619 ± 0.0250^b
500mM	0.6428 ± 0.0577^a
S.E	0.014
F-stat	398.857
P-value	0.000
Sig.	*

Discussion

Plant growth, physiology, and antioxidant enzyme activities are susceptible to metal toxicity and elucidated through cell injury and plant tolerance levels against metal stress (Aslam et al.2021). In this present work, the plant height was rigorously affected when plants were exposed to lead contamination. Soares et al. (2001) reported that higher concentration of heavy metal has been reported to retard the cell division and differentiation, reduce their elongation and effect plant growth and development. The root and shoot length of the treated seedlings were also found to be considerably reduced at all levels of the heavy metals applied, except the control, where root length was more or less comparable with those of untreated seedlings (Figure 1 and 3). The adverse effects on root and shoot growth were much more pronounced at the higher concentration (500mM), which may be one aspect of the role of metabolic inhibitors in the overall phenomenon of plants growth. Many studies had reported an inhibitory effect of various heavy metals, including Cd and Pb, on plant growth (Sharma and Dubey 2005; Mishra et al., 2006). The result on number of leaves revealed that heavy metal affect the number of leaves, plants with the highest concentration of lead has the lowest number of leaves in both weeks. Same pathological changes in ultra-structure level were testified on other plant species by Goyal et al. (2020). Leaves are considered as one of the most important plant organs because of their role in capturing light and making food by the process of photosynthesis.

Farooqi et al. (2009) made a study on soybean which indicated that heavy metal toxicity induced a histological change in leaves, and made a thin leaf blade, minified the xylem and phloem in the vascular bundles, and also reduced the diameter of the xylem vessels. At the same time, all these damages could disrupt many plant activities including anti oxidative system, photosynthesis, respiration, mineral nutrition,

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

membrane structure and properties and gene expression (Figure 2). Furthermore, the observed negative impacts on sunflower physiology (Table 1) confirmed that lead concentration in the soil above tolerable limits poses a threat to plant physiological machinery, which results in chlorosis, necrosis, rolling and twisting of leaves, eventually impeded the plant health (Shabaan et al.,2020; Ahmed et al.,2022). My results are similar to previous studies that revealed severe adverse effects on plant growth and physiology under lead stress Carotenoids serve as antioxidants against free radicals and photochemical damage (Sengar et al., 2008). Result of current study reveal no significant ($p < 0.05$) change in chlorophyll a, and b and carotenoids. (Table 1), indicated that sunflower plant may has a high ability to tolerate lead stress. The deterioration of chlorophyll synthesis due to lead toxicity resulting in chlorotic leaves, changed ratios of chlorophyll a and b (Viehweger and Geipel, 2010) and photosynthetic activity. The exposure to lead decreased the dry matter significantly in experimental plants (Figure 5 and 7). The considerable reduction in dry matter yields of the plants under the influence of high concentrations of heavy metals is in agreement with significant reduction reported in dry biomass of Albizzia lebbek under the toxic effect of lead and cadmium Farooqi et al. (2009).

The growth-development, fresh-dry biomass and growth tolerance index of root, shoot and leaves were negatively altered by increasing lead concentrations in sunflower (Figure 4 and 6). Same results were obtained by some other studies at the calculated lead concentration: root, shoot and leaf growth, fresh and dry biomass were critically reduced Zea mays (Wang et al., 2021). The weight of the shoot was significantly higher than that of the roots. Other authors (Ashraf et al., 2019; Alaboudi et al.,2018) found reductions of dry matter production in many plant species as a function of the application of increasing doses of heavy metal in experiments with soil and nutrient solution. Based on the results in Table 3, it is clear that sunflower can uptake heavy metals to the plant tissue as previously reported by Spirochova et al., (2003). From the experimental data it was clear that the largest portion of lead taken up by the plant was stored in the roots rather than in stem and leaves. This is because heavy metals are absorbed by roots from soil solution and later on translocated to leaves (through xylem vessels) where they are deposited in vacuoles (de Abreu et al., 2017). Lead accumulation in roots is considered to be a factor that increases plant tolerance to lead toxicity, because it prevents the metal translocation to leaves (Azad et al., 2011). Based on the experimental data it is clear that as the concentration of lead in the soil increases the amount of metal taken up by the plant also increases.

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

From Table 3 it is clear that the lead concentration in the whole plant is less slightly than the metal concentration in the soil after harvesting. Based on lead accumulation in roots more than other parts of the plant, it could be concluded that roots play a very significant role in extra lead storage. The high lead concentration, found mainly in roots, suggested that sunflower tend to avoid toxicity in the physiologically most active portions of the plants by reducing lead translocation to the epigeous portion.

Conclusion

The problem of heavy metal pollution is continuously worsening due to a series of human activities, leading to intensification of the research dealing with the phytotoxicity of these contaminants and with the mechanisms used by plants to counter their harmful effects. Heavy metal pollutants like lead, undoubtedly cause deleterious effects in plants. In this study, the tolerance limits and mechanisms of heavy metal tolerance of sunflower were assessed against three levels each of lead exposure. All the growth parameters were affected at different concentration. These findings are relevant to evaluate the effect of heavy metal pollutants on sunflower and assess the tolerance levels of the plant. The results from this study would certainly be useful to find strategies to alleviate sunflower from heavy metal stress and also to explore and enhance its phytoremediation potential.

Recommendations

1. The level of potentially toxic heavy metals and metalloids in water, sediments, soils and the resident biota should be assessed and monitored regularly
2. The public should be educated about the harmful effects of toxic heavy metals on human health and the environment.
3. The native plant proposed in this research can be effectively used in practical applications of phytoremediation with the aim of remediating soil contaminated by heavy metals around metal smelting factories and mining sites etc.

Acknowledgements

My gratitude goes to my supervisors, Dr. A.M. Gumi and Dr I. M Magami for their supports, supervisory skills, motivation, Encouragement and intellectual contribution to the success of this research, my sincere gratitude goes to my Parent, Husband and Children for their prayers and patience, may Allah bless you all.

References

(*Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025*)

Alaboudi, K.A., Ahmed, B. & Brodie, G. (2018). Phytoremediation of Pb and Cd contaminated soils by using sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) plant. *Annals of Agricultural Sciences*, 63 (1):123-127

Altaf, A.R., Teng, H., Saleem, M., Ahmad, H.R, Adi, I M & Shahzad, K. (2020.) Associative interplay of pseudomonas gessardii BLP141 and pressmud ameliorated growth, physiology, yield, and Pb-toxicity in sunflower. *Bioremediat J.* 25(2):178–188. doi:10.1080/10889868.2020.1853028.

Alvarez, M.E., Nota, F and Cambiagno, D.A. (2010) Epigenetic control of plant immunity. *Mol Plant Pathol* 11:563–576.

Ahmad, S., Liu, X., Tang, J & Zhang, S. (2022). Biochar-supported nanosized zero-valent iron (nZVI/BC) composites for removal of nitro and chlorinated contaminants. *Chem Eng J.* 431:133187.

Ashraf, I., Ahmad, F., Sharif, A., Altaf, A.R & Teng, H. (2021). Heavy metals assessment in water, soil, vegetables and their associated health risks via consumption of vegetables, District Kasur, Pakistan. *SN Appl Sci.* 3(5):552. doi:10.1007/s42452-021-04547-y.

Ashraf, S., Ali, Q., Zahir, Z.A., Sobia, A & Asghar H.N. (2019). Phytoremediation: environmentally sustainable way for reclamation of heavy metal polluted soils. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf.* 174:714–727. doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.02.068.

Aslam, M., Aslam, A., Sheraz, M., Ali, B., Ulhassan, Z., Najeeb, U., Zhou, W & Gill, R.A. (2021). Lead toxicity in cereals: mechanistic insight into toxicity, mode of action, and management. *Front Plant Sci.* 11.

Awofolu, O.R. (2015). A survey of trace metals in vegetation, soil and lower animal along some selected major roads in metropolitan city of Lagos. *Environmental Monitoring Assessment* 105 (1-3): 431-447.

Azad, H. N., Shiva, A. H. & Malekpour, R. (2011). Toxic effects of lead on growth and some biochemical and ionic parameters of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) seedlings. *Current Research Journal of Biological Sciences*, Taiwan, 3 (4): 398-403.

Batista, A.A., Santos, J.A.J., Bomfim, M.R., Moreira, F.M., Leal, E.F & da Conceição, J.N. (2017). Induced changes in the growth of four plant species due to lead toxicity. *Revista Brasileira de Engenharia Agrícola e Ambiental*, 21(5):327-332.

Black, C.A. (2015). Methods of soil analysis. Vol.1. *Amer. Soc. Agron.* Madison, Wisconsin.

(*Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025*)

- Chen, X.X., Liu, Y.M., Zhao, Q.Y., Cao, W.Q., Chen, X.P and Zou C.Q. (2020). Health risk assessment associated with heavy metal accumulation in wheat after long-term phosphorus fertilizer application. *Environ. Pollut.* 2020; 262:114348. doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114348.
- de Abreu, C.B., do Sacramento, B.L., Alves, A.T., Moura, S.C., Pinelli, M. S & Neto, A.D.d-Z. (2017). Nutritional and biochemical changes induced by lead in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*). *Semina: Ciências Agrárias, Londrina*, 37 (3) 1229- 1242.
- Falcioni, R., Antunes, W.C., Demattê, J.A.M. & Nanni, M.R. (2023). Biophysical, Biochemical, and Photochemical Analyses Using Reflectance Hyperspectroscopy and Chlorophyll a Fluorescence Kinetics in Variegated Leaves. *Biology* 2023, 12, 704.
- Farmaha., Bhupinder. Singh., William. Caughman. & Dara Park. Precision Agriculture Based Soil Sampling Strategies. (2020).
- Farooqi, M., Zafar, Iqbal., Kabir, M & Shafiq, M. (2009). Toxic effects of lead and cadmium on germination and seedling growth of *Albizia lebeck (L.)*, *Benth, J. Bot.*, 2009, 41(1): 27-33.
- Fulekar, M.H. (2016). Phytoremediation of heavy metals by *Helianthus annuus* in aquatic and soil environment. *Int.J. Curr. Microbiol. App.Sci.*, 5(7): 392-404.
- Ghani, A. (2011). Effect of chromium toxicity on growth, chlorophyll and some mineral nutrients of *brassica juncea L.* *Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences, H. Botany*, 2011. Vol. 2: p. 9 -15.
- Goyal, D., Yadav, A., Prasad, M., Singh, T.B., Shrivastav, P., Ali, A., Dantu, P.K. & Mishra, S. (2020). Effect of heavy metals on plant growth: an overview. *Contaminants in agriculture*, 2020, pp.79-101.
- He, L., Dai, Z., Liu, X., Tang, C & Xu J. (2021). Effect of alkaline lignin on immobilization of cadmium and lead in soils and the associated mechanisms. *Chemosphere*. 281:130969. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130969.
- Hinkelmann, Klaus & Kempthorne, Oscar. (2008). Design and Analysis of Experiments, Volume I: *Introduction to Experimental Design* (Second ed.).
- Hong, Y.K., Kim, J.W., Lee, S.P., Yang, J.E & Kim S.C. (2022). Effect of combined soil amendment on immobilization of bioavailable As and Pb in paddy soil. *Toxics*. 10 (2). doi:10.3390/toxics10020090.

(Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025)

Hou, R., Wang, L., O'Connor, D., Tsang, D.C.W., Rinklebe J & Hou, D. (2020). Effect of immobilizing reagents on soil Cd and Pb lability under freeze-thaw cycles: implications for sustainable agricultural management in seasonally frozen land. *Environ Int.* 144:106040. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2020.106040.

Liu, R., Bai, L., Liu, M., Wang, R., Wu, Y., Li, Q., Ba, Y., Zhang, H., Zhou, G., Yu, F & Huang H. (2022). Combined exposure of lead and high-fat diet enhanced cognitive decline via interacting with CREB-BDNF signaling in male rats. *Environ Pollut.* 304:119200. doi:10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2022.119200.

Lyu, H., He, Y., Tang, J., Hecker, M., Liu, Q., Jones, P.D., Codling, G & Giesy, J.P. (2016). Effect of pyrolysis temperature on potential toxicity of biochar if applied to the environment. *Environ Pollut.* 218:1–7. doi:10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2016.08.014.

Lyu, H., He, Y., Tang, J., Hecker, M., Liu, Q., Jones, P.D., Codling G & Giesy J.P. (2016). Effect of pyrolysis temperature on potential toxicity of biochar if applied to the environment. *Environ Pollut.* 218:1–7. doi:10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2016.08.014.

Mishra, S., Srivastava, S., Tripathi, R., Kumar, R., Seth, C & Gupta, D. (2006). Lead detoxification by coontail (*Ceratophyllum demersum* L.) involves induction of phytochelatins and antioxidant system in response to its accumulation. *Chemosphere*, 65(6):1027–1039.

Najeeb, U., Ahmad, W., Zia, M.H., Zaffar, M & Zhou, W. (2017). Enhancing the lead phytostabilization in wetland plant *Juncus effusus* L. through somaclonal manipulation and EDTA enrichment. *Arab J Chem.* 10:S3310–S3317.

Rehman, S., Chattha, M.U., Khan, I., Mahmood, A., Hassan, M.U., Al-Huqail, A.A., Salem M.Z.M., Ali, H.M., Hano, C & El-Esawi, M.A. (2022). Exogenously applied trehalose augments Cadmium stress tolerance and yield of Mung Bean (*Vigna radiata* L.) grown in soil and hydroponic systems through reducing Cd uptake and enhancing photosynthetic efficiency and antioxidant defense systems. *Plants.* 11(6). doi:10.3390/plants11060822.

Shabaan, M., Asghar, H.N., Akhtar, M.J., Ali, Q & Ejaz M. (2020.) Role of plant growth promoting rhizobacteria in the alleviation of lead toxicity to *Pisum sativum* L. *Int J Phytoremediation.* 0(0):1–9.

Sharma, P & Dubey, R.S. (2005). Lead toxicity in plants. *Brazilian Journal of plant physiology*, 17(1): 35-52.

(*Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025*)

Sengar, R.S., Gupta, S., Gautam, M., Sharma, A & Sengar, K. (2008). Occurrence, uptake, accumulation and physiological responses of nickel in plants and its effects on enviro. *Res. J. Phytochemistry*, 2:44-60.

Soares, C.R.F.S., Graziotti, P.H., Siquaira, J.O & Carvalho, J. H. De. (2001). Zinc toxicity on growth and nutrition of *Eucalyptus muculata* and *Eucalyptus arophylla*. *Pesq. Agrop. Brasileira*, 36: 339-348.

Spirochova, I. K., Puncocharova, J., Kafka, Z., Kubal, M., Soudek, P & Vanek, T. (2003). 'Accumulation of heavy metals by in vitro cultures of plants', *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution Focus*, 3: 269-276.

Viehweger, K & Geipel, G. (2010). Uranium accumulation and tolerance in *Arabidopsis halleri* under native versus hydroponic conditions. *Environ. Exp. Botany*, 69; 39-46.

Wang, Y., Chen, S., Deng, C., Shi, X., Cota-Ruiz, K., White, J.C., Zhao, L & Gardea-Torresdey J.L. (2021). Metabolomic analysis reveals dose-dependent alteration of maize (*Zea mays* L.) metabolites and mineral nutrient profiles upon exposure to zerovalent iron nanoparticles. *NanoImpact*. 23:100336.

Xie, X., Liu, Y., Qiu, H & Yang, X. (2020). Quantifying ecological and human health risks of heavy metals from different sources in farmland soils within a typical mining and smelting industrial area. *Environ Geochem Health*. doi:10.1007/s10653-020-00731-y.

Zhang, Y., Hou, D., O'Connor, D., Shen, Z., Shi, P., Ok, Y.S., Tsang, D.C.W., Wen, Y & Luo, M. (2019). Lead contamination in Chinese surface soils: source identification, spatial-temporal distribution and associated health risks. *Crit Rev Environ Sci Technol*. 49(15):1386-1423. doi:10.1080/10643389.2019.1571354.